

READING STRATEGIES AND READING COMPREHENSION OF GRADE VI STUDENTS

MARILYN B. PANGILINAN¹

DR. CECILIA Q. VELASCO²

F17-fs-eng@lspu.edu.ph¹

cecilia.velasco@lspu.edu.ph²

ORCID No. 0000-0001-6382-9367

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City Campus, San Pablo Laguna, Philippines

ABSTRACT

This study focused in determining the reading strategies and reading comprehension of the Grade VI students. Intermediate pupils in Palagaran Elementary School, in Tiaong II District, Tiaong, Quezon were chosen as the respondents of the study. The one-group pre-test and post-test reading comprehension test was used as the main data-gathering instrument. Preparatory measures were conducted before the implementation of the study; some permission letters were also prepared. The one-group pre-test and post-test reading comprehension test have been validated and corrected by external and internal experts. The result of the variables showed a significant difference between the reading strategies and the reading comprehension of students in English in terms of literal, interpretive and evaluative. However, the result of the study may be affected by modular way of learning, wherein pupils are being guided by parents or tutors at home. Through this result, as for the recommendations, the teachers may use and modify the reading strategies to be used effectively to comprehend the passage or story in English among the pupils, the pupils may also use supplementary activities to improve and enhance their reading comprehension in English through practice and mastery, and the future researchers may conduct similar or more complex study in line with this.

Keywords: reading strategies, reading comprehension, literal, interpretive and evaluative